

MonLog: MONotonic-constrained LOGistic Regressions for Automated Safety Curve Design

Alessandro Melone¹, Robin Jeanne Kirschner¹, Dirk Müller², Abdalla Swikir¹ and Sami Haddadin¹

Abstract—The increasing integration of robots in close human environments necessitates robust safety measures that can adapt to evolving tasks and conditions. Current standards rely on task-specific safety evaluations that are often inflexible, requiring repeated assessments whenever task parameters change. This work proposes *MonLog*, a data-driven, probabilistic method to automatically derive safety curves (SCs) from recent injury protection data sets. By leveraging non-linear modeling techniques, our approach addresses the limitations of conventional linear SCs, which often result in overly conservative speed restrictions. We present a comprehensive test routine to validate our method, highlighting improvements in both compliance with safety constraints and operational efficiency. Our findings demonstrate that the proposed approach not only enhances safety but also optimizes robotic performance, making it suitable for a wide range of applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring human safety in close proximity to robots is increasingly critical with the rise of social robots, medical support systems, and industrial collaborative applications [1], [2]. As a result, there is a growing interest in developing reliable safety thresholds [3]–[6]. The existing safety thresholds in safety standards require experimental analysis of collision forces, comparing them to permissible values [7]. This certifiable method, based on task-specific risk assessments, lacks flexibility as it requires reevaluation with any task change. To enhance flexibility, researchers propose human tracking and model-based solutions for dynamic safe robot control, such as using human body models for force limits and speed monitoring [8], [9]. Additionally, energy-based velocity scaling using injury protection datasets has been suggested for real-time robot control [5], [10], [11].

This method of robot injury prevention necessitates an extensive amount of injury protection datasets and a robust correlation between the mass-velocity data of a robot and labeled injury data, referred to as *safety curves (SCs)* [10]. Recent studies have concentrated on developing the injury protection datasets by suggesting experimental setups, methodologies, and preliminary trials [5], [12]. Nevertheless, as illustrated in Fig. 1, the established mass-velocity datasets with annotated injury data can only be utilized for real-time robotic control if each dataset is accompanied by a corresponding SC. To date, these SCs have been modeled using linear regression for simplicity and due to small size of the expensive injury protection datasets [10]. However, this method may limit

Fig. 1: Labeled injury datasets from experimental analysis are used to derive safety curves (SCs) respecting robot mass, velocity, and curvature information. To obtain ideal SCs different approaches need to be evaluated for efficiency, validated for accurate injury classification, and tested for practical feasibility before implementation.

robotic performance by enforcing excessively conservative speed restrictions. For instance, a robot with a low effective mass could still operate safely at higher speeds, but the linear model might unnecessarily lower its speed limit. To cope with data scarcity (≈ 20 datapoints) [12], domain-specific knowledge can be infused into the model [13], such as assuming monotonicity [14], [15]. Additionally, the physical model proposed by ISO/TS suggests that a nonlinear safety constraint would be more appropriate.

In this paper, we introduce a novel method for deriving SCs called *MonLog*, which employs *Monotonic-constrained Logistic* regressions to infer SCs from the 1-st to 3-rd order and automatically selects the optimal solution based on a set of relevant metrics. We demonstrate this method using real injury protection datasets from recent studies on human hand injuries (substituted by pig feet) [12]. We begin by outlining the key requirements for the SCs based on current state-of-the-art approaches. Subsequently, we present the features of *MonLog*, which are designed to generate SCs that fulfill all relevant criteria. Finally, we derive the SCs and conduct a rigorous testing routine to evaluate the robot’s compliance with the SC constraints, enabling an objective assessment of both efficiency and constraint satisfaction metrics.

II. STATE OF THE ART SAFETY CURVES

Two primary methods for generating velocity-shaping SCs are found in the literature: one based on datasets of masses, velocities, and injuries [10], and the other on force and pressure thresholds converted into mass and velocity SCs using simplified physical contact models [7].

In the first method, injury data from various impactor

¹Munich Institute of Robotics and Machine Intelligence (MIRMI), Technical University of Munich (TUM), Munich, Germany
alessandro.melone@tum.de

² Department of Orthopaedics and Sports Orthopaedics, Klinikum Rechts der Isar, TUM School of Medicine, Technical University of Munich, 81675 Munich, Germany

shapes are plotted onto the mass-velocity constellation. *Key impact points* are used to fit a linear regression (LR), resulting in an SC bounded by maximum (e.g., 4.5 m/s) and minimum (e.g., 0.1 m/s) velocity limits to ensure safe and efficient robot operation [10]. This method benefits from employing linear regression, which is widely understood due to its popularity and involves only two free parameters — an advantageous feature given the limited size of the datasets in this context. However, it fails to fully utilize the available information, as the model fitting relies on only a subset of data points. Additionally, the method does not ensure the monotonicity of the SC, specifically the negative slope of the line, which is undesirable in highly automated environments.

The second method, outlined in ISO/TS 15066:2016 [7], calculates the robot’s speed limit based on maximum pressure and force limits. This relationship assumes fully inelastic contact between the robot and a specific human body part. The maximum relative velocity between the robot and the human, i.e., the SC value, is expressed by

$$v_{rel,max} = \frac{F_{max}}{\sqrt{\mu k}}, \quad (1)$$

where F_{max} is the maximum permissible force, k is the effective spring constant of the body area, and with

$$\mu = \left(\frac{1}{m_H} + \frac{1}{m_R} \right)^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

being the reduced mass of the two-body system, where m_H and m_R are the human body part effective mass and robot effective mass, respectively. The terms in Eq.(1) are obtained via experiments observing the human onset of pain thresholds by pressure and force measurement with a flat contact surface between human and robot.

Both methods yield SCs with strict boundaries. However, due to the variability in injury incidence among individuals (e.g., fractures occurring at 1011- 2129 N, with outliers up to 291 N [16]), it is essential to include probability information for injury occurrence. Thus, the SC inference problem should be framed as a classification task that provides probability ranges for different violation types.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we outline the requirements for inferring SCs and introduce our method, *MonLog*, for generating SCs. The SCs are derived as the decision boundary of a logistic regression classifier with polynomial feature transformations of various orders, ensuring the smoothness of the curve (Sec. III-A). Inferring SCs is challenging due to the scarcity of labeled data ($\simeq 20$ datapoints) and the high cost of obtaining additional labels [12]. To address these challenges, we incorporate domain-specific knowledge into our learning method [13], [17], [18]. In particular, increasing mass and/or velocity corresponds to an increment of the probability of injury, which translates to monotonicity constraint [14], [15] that we impose during the classifier training (Sec. III-B). Additionally, we integrate knowledge about injury severity by weighting misclassification errors accordingly (Sec. III-C). Prioritizing human safety, we conservatively bias the SC towards safety, following the approach in [10] (Sec. III-D). We tune model parameters and choose the regularization term to achieve two

TABLE I: Requirements for Safety Curve Design

Req.	Curve property	MonLog
physics-informed	monotonicity smoothness	imposed via constrained optimization property of the chosen model
motion efficiency	area under the curve	direct optimization and/or model selection
constraint satisfaction	low steepness	model selection

TABLE II: Polynomial Features Transformation

Notation	Expression $f(m, v)$
f_1	$[m, v]^T$
f_2	$[m, v, m^2, mv, v^2]^T$
$f_{2,io}$	$[m, v, mv]^T$
f_3	$[m, v, m^2, mv, v^2, m^3, m^2v, mv^2, v^3]^T$
$f_{3,io}$	$[m, v, mv, m^2v, mv^2]^T$
f_p	$[mv^2]^T$

key objectives: first, to ensure sufficiently low steepness for effective constraint satisfaction when implemented on a real robot using the SMU model; and second, to enhance motion efficiency by increasing the area under the curve (Sec. III-E) with or without a direct optimization introducing a term in the cost function (Sec. III-F).

These classifier features and the proposed methods are summarized in Tab. I. The following subsections provide detailed explanations of these methods and their application in MonLog.

A. Safety Curve from probabilistic model

For each impactor and body part, a dataset $D = \{(m_i, v_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ of N experiments is collected, where m_i and v_i are mass and velocity at collision time of the impactor of the i -th experiment, respectively. Moreover, $y_i \in \{\overline{\text{inj}}, \text{inj}\}$ denotes the occurrence or not of injury in the i -th experiment; In this work, the injury event is encoded as $\overline{\text{inj}} = 1$ while no injury as $\text{inj} = 0$. The dataset D allows fitting a model $p(m, v) \in [0, 1]$ that approximates $\Pr(\overline{\text{inj}}|m, v)$, i.e., the probability of injury given mass and velocity. To achieve that, we consider a logistic regression model with polynomial features transformation:

$$p(m, v) = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v))}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v))}, \quad (3)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$ is a polynomial function with two variables (m and v) and p terms with all coefficients equal to one, while $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ are the model parameters fitted to the data set. Therefore, $\beta^T f(m, v)$ is a polynomial function with coefficients β .

Once $p(m, v)$ is fitted, every couple (m, v) can be classified as unsafe (i.e., likely to determine an injury), depending if the estimated probability of injury is higher than a user-defined threshold p_{\max} . In formulas:

$$p(m, v) \geq p_{\max} \Rightarrow (m, v) \text{ is } \textit{unsafe}, \quad (4)$$

where $p_{\max} \in (0, 1)$. The points of the mass-velocity plane that satisfy

$$p(m, v) = p_{\max}, \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2: Exemplary safety curves (in black) and probabilistic injury model (shown as gradient-colored contours) derived using monotonicity-constrained logistic regression with various polynomial feature transformations (see Tab. II). Colored data points indicate injury severity (see Sec. III-C).

belong to the sought SC , which is known as *decision boundary* in classification settings. Notice that these points respect as well

$$\frac{p(m, v)}{1 - p(m, v)} = \frac{p_{\max}}{1 - p_{\max}}, \quad (6)$$

and that, from Eq. (3), it is easy to show that

$$\log\left(\frac{p(m, v)}{1 - p(m, v)}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v), \quad (7)$$

where the left-hand side is the so-called *logit*. Therefore, the SC has an expression equal to

$$\beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v) = \log\left(\frac{p_{\max}}{1 - p_{\max}}\right), \quad (8)$$

which means that the functional shape of the SC is equal to the one of the polynomial $f(m, v)$. The ability to express a smooth probability distribution over mass and velocity and the direct relationship between the SC and the polynomial feature transformation are the main arguments for applying logistic regression to the problem at hand.

B. Imposing monotonicity

Commonly the Maximum Likelihood method is used to fit logistic regression models. It chooses the model parameters (β_0 and β in our case) for which the probability of the observed sample is maximized. The log-likelihood function for a logistic regression model with polynomial features transformation is [19]

$$l(\beta_0, \beta) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \left\{ y_i (\beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v)) - \log(1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v))) \right\}, \quad (9)$$

where $w_i \in \mathbb{R}$ is the weight of the i -th experiment depending on the severity of injury. The monotonicity of the probability distribution can be expressed via

$$\nabla p(m, v) \triangleq \left[\frac{\partial p(m, v)}{\partial m}, \frac{\partial p(m, v)}{\partial v} \right]^T \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

$$\forall (m, v) \in [m_{\min}, m_{\max}] \times [v_{\min}, v_{\max}],$$

where m_{\min} , m_{\max} , v_{\min} , and v_{\max} are the minimum and maximum mass and velocity given by the application, respectively. Inserting Eq. (3) in Eq. (10), results in:

$$\nabla p(m, v) \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow \beta^T \nabla f(m, v) \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

Maximizing the log-likelihood while satisfying the monotonicity constraint can be formulated in a numerical optimization problem as

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\beta_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \beta \in \mathbb{R}^p} \quad & C l(\beta_0, \beta) - r(\beta), \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \beta^T \nabla f(m_k, v_k) \geq 0, \quad \forall (m_k, v_k) \in \Gamma_m \times \Gamma_v, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $r(\beta)$ is a regularization term preventing the model from overfitting the data and $C \in \mathbb{R}$ is a tuning parameter of the regularization strength: smaller values imply stronger regularization. Moreover, Γ_m and Γ_v are the set of gridpoints from the discretization of $[m_{\min}, m_{\max}]$ and $[v_{\min}, v_{\max}]$ with constant stepsize Δm and Δv , respectively.

C. Cost-sensitive learning

When the injury type is annotated in the dataset, we can employ the Cost-sensitive learning framework [20] weighting samples based on injury severity in the cost function in Eq.(9). Assigning higher weights ($w_i \in \mathbb{R}$) for severe injuries increases the classifier's estimated injury probabilities for these cases.

The weights have values greater than one only for injuries classified as such (i.e., if $y_i = 1$). The weight corresponds to the number of recovery days for the injury, normalized to the maximum recovery days for skin indentation. Recovery days are estimated as follows. For no observable injury or minor skin indentations, we assume no injury or a slight contusion without mobility or work restrictions, resulting in 0 ~ 3 days ($w_i = 1.0$, $y_i = 0$). Skin cuts, potentially requiring sutures, typically heal after suture removal in 10 ~ 14 days for the dorsum of the hand [21] ($w_i = 3.5$, $y_i = 1$)¹. Bone recovery takes 6 ~ 8 weeks [22] ($w_i = 14.0$, $y_i = 1$).

An alternative approach to incorporate injury severity is multiclass classification. However, this method is suboptimal due to our limited dataset size, potentially leading to imbalanced classes in a One-vs-Rest approach or exacerbating the data scarcity in a One-vs-One approach [23].

D. Null in-sample injury misclassification

Since human safety is paramount, the model parameters should be inferred as accurately as possible. The literature suggests a much higher number of samples than the available

¹Note that required suture in any of the skin cuts in [12] is highly unlikely and only serves as conservative estimation.

TABLE III: Regularization terms for Eq.12

Name	Expression $r(\beta)$
Lasso	$\sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j $
Ridge	$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p (\beta_j)^2$
Elastic Net	$\frac{1-\rho}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p (\beta_j)^2 + \rho \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j $

one to reliably estimate the model parameters [24]–[26]. In particular, the statistical analysis carried out in [27] suggests a minimum number of samples equal to minimum sample size $n = 500$ or $n = 100 + 50i$ where i is the number of independent variables of the model in order to correctly estimate the coefficient of the logistic regression model. Unfortunately, the best currently available datasets for our application contain approximately twenty samples ($N \simeq 20$) for each body part and impactor [12]. Therefore, we propose following the approach of [10], which assumes as safe an SC that lies below any injury data point. This is achieved by shifting down the line obtained by linear regression until all the injury data points are above the line. In our approach, this is equivalent to individualizing the SC referring to the highest p_{\max} , which still avoids misclassification of injuries in the dataset. Moreover, we shift the curve downwards of a user-defined safety margin (here, we chose 0.05 m/s).

E. Regularization and model selection

We compared three regularization terms shown in Tab. III. Ridge regularization has the effect of shrinking the estimates of β_j towards zero, but they never are exactly zero (unless $C = 0$ in Eq. (12)). Instead, Lasso regularization tends to set some of the coefficients β_j equal to zero [19]. Elastic Net is a mixture of both approaches regulating which regularization is predominant via the parameter ρ .

In statistical learning, model selection aims to choose the best model for unseen data [19], [28], typically by using a validation set or cross-validation, which are both impractical due to the data scarcity of our problem. Moreover, since the priority is safety, which translates into avoiding in-sample misclassification of injury data points (as discussed in Sec. III-D), we propose model selection based on maximizing the area under the SC (AUSC) for performance.

F. Direct optimization of motion efficiency

To further improve performance, we propose to combine model search with the introduction of an additional term in the cost function to increase the AUSC. The term penalizes the squared difference between the logit and a user-defined parameter $\sigma \in (0, 1)$:

$$c(\beta) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{(m,v) \in \mathcal{C}} (\beta_0 + \beta^T f(m, v) - \sigma)^2, \quad (13)$$

where the set \mathcal{C} is constructed from the dataset $D = \{(m_i, v_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, and $|\mathcal{C}|$ is the cardinality of \mathcal{C} . In particular, the construction of \mathcal{C} begins by sorting D in ascending order based on the m -values, yielding D_s . The set \mathcal{C} is initialized as empty, and an auxiliary variable \tilde{v} is set to inf . The algorithm then iterates over each pair (m_k, v_k) in D_s . If $v_k < \tilde{v}$, the value of \tilde{v} is updated to v_k , and the pair (m_k, v_k) is added to

Fig. 3: Trajectories employed in tests, and their initial $p(0)$ and final $p(t_f)$ points in the Cartesian robot base frame.

	$p(0)$	$p(t_f)$
T1	0.2901	0.5377
	0.2270	-0.3159
	0.6452	0.1554
T2	0.4064	0.7067
	0.0296	0.0297
T3	0.8407	0.1395
	0.2023	0.6337
	0.0223	0.0225
	0.7372	0.7366
T4	0.5046	0.5025
	-0.3450	0.5575
	0.3686	0.3680

\mathcal{C} . Otherwise, the pair (m_k, \tilde{v}) is added to \mathcal{C} to ensure that \mathcal{C} secures a non-increasing trend of v , avoiding conflict between the penalization term $c(\beta)$ and the monotonicity constraint.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

To validate the safety curve design procedure, we consider six injury protection data sets on unconstrained collision injuries obtained in an experimental series, where the human back of the hand and fingers are substituted with pig feet [12]. The dataset divides the injury types into *none* if no damage was observed after the collision, *skin indent* if a recovering indentation was observed, *skin cut* for clear openings in epidermis or dermis, and *tendon/bone injury* for any damages detected in tendon or bone tissue. Moreover, we applied the ISO/TS model in Eq. (1) using the F_{\max} values provided by the dataset in [12], together with body mass m_H and stiffness k provided by ISO/TS itself.

For each data set, a model is created for each of the six polynomial feature transformations shown in Fig. 2 varying C in Eq. (12) in the set $\{0.1, 2.58, 5.05, 7.5, 10.0\}$ and for all the loss functions in Tab.III. This originated a total of sixty classifiers for each dataset that are compared to find the one with the highest AUSC while avoiding misclassification of the injury data points in the dataset. Moreover, a safety tolerance, i.e., the minimum distance between the safety curve and the injury data points along the vertical axis, is set to 0.05 m/s. The considered AUSC is the definite integral of the SC for $m \in [2, 8]$, which is computed via numerical integration. The search is repeated again, optimizing the AUSC (see Sec. III-F). Therefore, a safety curve is obtained from MonLog and optimized MonLog for each dataset. The discretization steps Δv and Δm are both set to 0.5 for all the polynomials in Tab. II except for f_3 and $f_{3,io}$ for which they are set to 0.1 and 0.2, respectively. The set Γ_m and Γ_v are defined using $m_{\min} = 0.1$ and $v_{\min} = 0.1$, while m_{\max} and v_{\max} are equal to the maximum mass and velocity in the considered dataset, respectively.

The problem of Eq.(12) being convex allows the employment of efficient convex solvers. Therefore, building upon `clogistic` [29] that implements a logistic regression model with linear constraints compliant with the `scikit-learn` [30] framework using the `cvxpy` [31], [32] solver, we implemented a logistic regression solver with monotonicity constraints of the probability distributions for the considered

Fig. 4: Robot reflected-mass over Cartesian path length for test trajectories.

feature transformations².

1) *Setup*: The obtained safety curves are tested for their constraint satisfaction and efficiency with a Franka Emika robot during a free-motion trajectory tracking task. The robot is tasked to follow a set of trajectories inspired by the robot reference cube based on ISO9283:1998 [33], which initial and final points in the robot base frame are defined in Fig. 3. These trajectories replicate common workspace motions in which a noticeable change in effective mass is observed (see Fig. 4) to assess the suitability of the optimized SCs. The robot is controlled through FE Franka Control Interface (FCI) using the C++ library libfranka [34] and all trajectories have a trapezoidal velocity profile [35] with maximum acceleration 2.0 m/s^2 and maximum velocity 1.7 m/s . We implement the SMU module in line with [10] and set a minimum velocity of 0.1 m/s to avoid stopping the robot close to singularities. The reflected inertia m_u calculation (i.e., the input m of the SC) is performed according to [36]. Moreover, we considered the presence of an additional payload of 1 kg attached to the end-effector to resemble typical operational conditions.

2) *Measurement Protocol, Processing and Evaluation*: For all six data sets, we compared the performance of four SCs: MonLog, optimized MonLog (see Sec. III-F), LR, and ISO. These curves were tested for tracking the four trajectories in Fig. 3, where each measurement procedure is repeated three times in a row, resulting in 528 experiments. The average execution times over all the experiments resulting from the SCs application are used to compare the efficiency of the SCs. To evaluate the constraint satisfaction imposed by the SCs, the time for which the robot velocity exceeds the maximum permitted over a threshold of 0.05 m/s^3 is measured.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following section, we begin by summarizing the derived safety curves and their evaluation. We then present the results of applying these SCs in robotic experiments to assess the feasibility of the resulting constraint. Finally, we provide a detailed discussion of the experimental outcomes.

A. Safety Curves

The SCs obtained for the dataset related to the human back of the hand (substituted by a pig foot) impacted by an edged impact geometry are shown in Fig. 5. Then, for each dataset, we found the models shown in Fig. 2 with the highest AUSC tuning their hyperparameters, and so we ranked

Fig. 5: Safety curves resulting a) MonLog, LR, and ISO. b) optimized MonLog (see Sec. III-F), LR, and ISO for the injury dataset of edged impact geometries hitting the back of the human hand.

TABLE IV: Ranking of polynomial feature transformations

	No Optimization								AUSC optimized							
	f_p	f_1	$f_{2,io}$	f_2	$f_{3,io}$	f_3	LR	ISO	f_p	f_1	$f_{2,io}$	f_2	$f_{3,io}$	f_3	LR	ISO
#1	0	3	0	1	1	5	2	0	0	1	0	1	2	7	1	0
#2	1	0	3	4	0	3	1	0	1	2	2	4	2	1	0	0
#3	1	0	4	0	3	1	2	1	0	0	4	3	3	2	0	0
#4	0	1	3	3	3	1	1	0	0	1	6	2	3	0	0	0
#5	0	4	1	1	4	2	0	0	1	5	0	1	2	2	1	0
#6	4	2	0	3	1	0	2	0	2	2	0	1	0	0	7	0
#7	6	1	1	0	0	0	4	0	8	1	0	0	0	0	3	0
#8	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8

them for their AUSC. Tab. IV shows the number of times a model got a specific ranking. For example, the first column shows that f_p was the 2nd in one dataset and 6th in four datasets, etc. Lastly, we analyze for all six datasets whether severe violations of constraints occurred. We observed that the model-based approach from ISO/TS misclassified injury data points in four datasets (i.e., the SC curve was above injury data points), and the data-based linear regression led to a monotonically increasing SC for the sheet impactor hitting a finger dataset.

B. Feasibility tests

Using the same dataset as in Fig. 5, by applying the SC from ISO, LR, and MonLog⁴ (i.e., the curve with the highest AUSC in Fig. 5(a)), we show the time evolution of the end-effector velocity in Fig. 6 and the corresponding measured robot reflected inertia and end-effector velocity in Fig. 7.

Considering the average metrics over all the experiments performed listed in Table V, the results indicate that MonLog reduced the average runtime of 5.99 % and 11.56 % compared to velocity scaling with linear regression (LR) and the model proposed in ISO/TS [7], respectively; while the optimized MonLog approach (see Sec. III-F) reduced it of 7.92 % and 13.37 %. Accordingly, MonLog increased the average velocity of 7.92 % and 4.54 % compared to LR and ISO, respectively; while optimized MonLog increased it of 12.82 % and 5.05 % compared to LR and ISO, respectively. Furthermore, MonLog reduced the average constraint activation time of 32.66 % and 10.40 % compared to ISO/TS and LR, respectively; while

²MonLogs code will be made publicly available upon acceptance

³The threshold is considered to take into account sensor noise.

⁴The model with the higher AUSC has $C = 7.5$, f_3 with $\beta_0 = -16.9$, $\beta = [5.45, 0, -0.72, 1.98, 0, 0.31, -0.06, -0.49, 0.11]^T$, and Lasso penalty.

TABLE V: Evaluation results of implemented safety curves

v_3	avg. time reduction		avg. time constraint activation	
	ISO/TS	LR	ISO/TS	LR
MonLog	11.56 %	5.99%	-32.66 %	-10.40%
MonLog opt.	13.37 %	7.92%	-34.80 %	-13.24%

Fig. 6: Time evolution of the Cartesian end-effector velocity of the trajectories defined in Fig. 3 for tested SC inference methods.

optimized MonLog reduced it of 34.80% and 13.24%. The percentage of time of constraint violation of the SCs, it is 0.117% with MonLog SCs, 0.123% with optimized MonLog, 0.002% with LR, and 0.003% with ISO/TS. The maximum constraint violation over all the experiments is 0.057 m/s for LR, 0.055 m/s for ISO, 0.072 m/s for MonLog, and 0.067 m/s for optimized MonLog. The constraint violations was observed only performing trajectories T1 and T2 with velocity 0.86 ± 0.11 m/s.

C. Discussion

In all the considered datasets, the MonLog approach successfully identified an SC validated in practical experiments. As shown in Tab. IV, the function f_3 consistently yielded the highest AUC across most datasets. Therefore, we recommend restricting the search to f_3 when computational resources are limited. The ISO/TS model, using measured average injury forces and ISO-provided estimates for human body part mass and stiffness, exhibited high misclassification rates (4 out of 6 datasets). Consequently, for SC design, this model should either be avoided or, if used, employ the most conservative assumptions for permissible contact forces rather than the mean forces in [12]. In the feasibility tests, MonLog SCs exhibited a higher average percentage of time with constraint violations compared to LR and ISO/TS. However, the brevity (the longest lasting only 0.008 s) and infrequency of these events suggest more conclusive validation in future experiments with a high-precision external measurement method, such as laser tracking, rather than internal joint position encoders. Moreover, violations occur predominantly at higher velocities and are limited to trajectories T1 and

Fig. 7: Relationship between cartesian end-effector velocity and robot reflected-mass of the trajectories defined in Fig. 3.

T2, where gravitational forces adversely affect deceleration⁵. Therefore, we recommend adopting a safety threshold higher than 0.05 m/s or employing velocity controllers for accurate tracking with high operational speed [38] to benefit fully from the higher average velocities enabled by MonLog. Lastly, expanding injury protection datasets enables inference of SCs with confidence bounds, facilitating the determination of maximum constraint violation thresholds.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presents MonLog, a machine learning-based approach for generating safety curves (SCs) from labeled injury protection datasets. MonLog incorporates domain-specific constraints and application-specific objectives to define safe and efficient robot velocity limits. By leveraging monotonicity-constrained logistic regression with polynomial feature transformations and a cost-sensitive loss function, MonLog optimizes motion performance while ensuring safety compliance. Tested on six injury protection datasets, MonLog outperformed existing SC methods, improving motion time efficiency by over 5.99% without violating application requirements. We recommend further investigation into human injury data to address data scarcity and enable more robust probabilistic assessments with confidence bounds.

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⁵The controller used employs gravity compensation provided by libfranka library [34], although more accurate Franka Emika robot dynamic parameters are available [37].

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